

The MDT Trigger Processor upgrade for ATLAS Muons at the HL-LHC

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Abstract

The Trigger Processor (TP) electronics for the Monitored Drift Tube (MDT) chambers (MDT-TP) is a key component in the upgrade of the first-level muon trigger for ATLAS at the High-Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC). The selectivity of the current system is limited by the moderate spatial resolution of the dedicated trigger chambers: Resistive Plate Chambers (RPC) and Thin Gap Chambers (TGC). The MDT-TP incorporates the high-resolution position measurements in the first level of the trigger to significantly improve the transverse momentum resolution of muon trigger candidates and to reduce the rate from mis-measured muons or accidental coincidences. The MDT-TP is designed to have a fixed latency of $1.7 \mu\text{s}$ in response to the incoming muon trigger candidate. The MDT-TP also provides the means to read out the MDT hits. In addition to the trigger and readout, the MDT-TP is responsible for configuring the MDT front-end electronics.

The MDT-TP is expected to reduce the muon trigger rate of the L0 trigger while keeping a high-efficiency plateau of 95% for a single muon trigger with a transverse momentum threshold of 20 GeV.

This poster describes the MDT-TP algorithms and their functionality, as well as the progress on the hardware developments. First results from complete system tests are also presented.

1 Introduction

The new first-level muon trigger (L0Muon) of the ATLAS experiment [1] will be upgraded to operate in the substantially increased luminosity environment of the HL-LHC. The selectivity of the current system is limited by the moderate spatial resolution of the dedicated trigger detectors: Resistive Plate Chambers (RPC) and Thin Gap Chambers (TGC) [2]. The Trigger Processor for the Monitored Drift Tube (MDT) chambers (MDT-TP) will make use of the high-resolution tracking capabilities of the MDT chambers to improve the transverse momentum P_T resolution and increase the sharpness of the muon level 0 trigger efficiency turn-on curves for the pre-selected RPC and TGC candidates provided by the Sector Logic (SL), as show in Figure 1. The MDT-TP is expected to reduce the output trigger rate by 50-70% while keeping high efficiency for muons with momenta above the P_T threshold of 20 GeV.

Figure 1: Performance plots for the ATLAS L0Muon MDT-TP: (left) the resolution of the reconstructed muons at the MDT-TP, as a function of the real P_T of the muon for the different methods of calculating the P_T and the total, (right) turn-on-curve for the L0Muon MDT-TP trigger with the 20 GeV threshold.

Architecture & Design: The MDT-TP system is built from 64 MDT-TP electronics boards, one per sector: 16 sectors distributed in the azimuth angle φ for 2 regions (barrel and endcap) and 2 sides (A and C). By design the MDT-TP system has a fixed latency of 1.764 μs in response to the incoming muon trigger candidate from (SL). The current algorithm implementation is capable of processing three simultaneous candidates. The MDT-TP also provides the means to read out the hits from the MDT chambers. In addition to the trigger and readout, the MDT-TP is responsible for configuring the MDT front-end electronics.

2 Hardware

The MDT-TP ATCA blade design is based on the open-source Apollo platform [3], comprised of two PCB modules:

Service Module (SM): is common to all Apollo applications, provides the ATCA Intelligent Platform Management Controller (IPMC) and the power entry and conditioning. It incorporates a powerful system-on-module (SoM) computer, Enclustra Mercury+, flexible clock and communications infrastructure.

Command Module (CM): application-specific module, provides the processing FPGA, as well as optical transceivers for communication with other ATLAS systems. Four demonstrators with the KU15p & ZU11EG FPGAs have been produced and tested to validate the capabilities and test the technology. Based on the experience with the demonstrators, two prototypes with the VU13P FPGA have been produced and are currently being integrated and tested to validate the final design.

The SoM will integrate the L0MDT services for control and monitoring of CM and the front end boards of the MDT chambers. Also will have the services for external systems such as Run Control & DCS.

Figure 2: (left) SM rev1 with the CM Prototype, (right) L0Muon MDT-TP functional diagram.

3 Firmware

3.1 DAQ

The **DAQ Level-0 Accept module** is a parameterizable and flexible concurrent timestamp-based data selection and packet formatting block. For each station of the MDT-TP project it is configured with 1 data stream, 4 output links, and 32 simultaneous searches.

3.2 Trigger path

The trigger path for the MDT-TP project involves several steps and components that work together to process the SL data proceeding from the fast RPC and TGC detectors to complement these measurements with the higher precision MDT spatial information to provide the higher resolution muon trigger momentum measurement.

The **Muon Candidate Manager (UCM)** receives and sorts the candidates from the SL to obtain the track angle and crossing position at each MDT station from the SL RPC/TGC seeds and manages the multi-threaded architecture.

The **Tube Address Remapping (TAR)** block calculates the MDT hit coordinates and pipelines them waiting for the candidate to arrive.

The **Hit Processor (HP)** filters the MDT hits in space and time using the candidate information to define the boundaries of the filters. The valid hits are then processed to obtain their drift radius and the local position of the tube with respect to the seed window is calculated.

The **Segment Finder (SF)** calculates the segment at each station and sends the position and angle to the momentum estimation block. Two different implementations are available with different algorithms: Legendre Transform SF (LSF) and Compact SF (CSF).

At the **P_T estimator** block, the muon track segments are combined to obtain the track momentum. Two algorithms are used depending on number of available segments: the sagitta algorithm when 3 segments are available and the deflection angle when 2 segments are available.

The algorithm is tested in parallel with two different frameworks: VHDL testbench & co-CTB framework. The firmware validation and algorithm tests for all firmware flavors are done automatically using gitlab continuous integration implemented using Hog (HDL-on-Git)[4].

Figure 3: Representation of the main different stages of the trigger path algorithm: (left) seed window formation and hit extraction, (center) Segments calculation, (right) momentum estimation.

4 Conclusions

The MDT-TP project is progressing. The hardware elements are already with the second revision of the SM and the CM in the prototyping stage and test stands at the various institutes and at CERN are ready and working.

All the main firmware blocks of the algorithm are developed, and in the process of being debugged, tested and validated. The current algorithm resources are within parameters and progress is being made to complete the integration of the firmware blocks and meet timing.

First integration tests with SL and CSM board had been done. FELIX computers with Phase 2 FELIX [5] prototype cards are installed in some of the test stands. The Core elements of SM are in place and being tested, the integration with external systems is being tested and validated with the other CERN and ATLAS teams such as Run Control & DCS.

References

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